

Study of Mukhapaka and its Modern Counterpart

Dr. Sayali M. Kewat¹ Dr. Sunil S. Kewat²

¹PG Scholar, Department of Shalaky Tantra, SMBT Ayurved Collage and Hospital Dhamangaon Nashik

²HOD & Professor, Department of Shalaky Tantra, Shivajirao Pawar Ayurvedic Medical College & Research Centre, Pachegaon, Ta.Newasa Dist.Ahilya Nagar

ABSTRACT: Mukhapaka described in Ayurveda, refers to inflammatory condition of the oral cavity, manifesting as ulcer, pain, redness and discomfort. Mukha Rogas is pittaja nanatmaja and rakta pradoshaja vikara and around 10% of population is suffering with this problem. Mukhapaka occurs due to Nutritional deficiency e.g. Vit.B12 deficiency, Folate deficiency, Stress, Illness, Poor oral hygiene, Eating hot food itmes, Leukaemia, Inflammatory bowel disease, Disturbances in G.I. tract like constipation, Poor hygiene etc. The modern counterpart of Mukhapaka is Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis, which can arise due to nutritional deficiencies, stress, infections, autoimmune disorders etc.

Ayurvedic management focuses on holistic healing through herbal formulations like Haritaki, Triphala, Yashtimadhu along with therapeutic procedures such as Kavala - Gandusha , Pratisarana. In modern medicine, topical analgesics, antiseptic mouthwashes, corticosteroids and nutritional supplements for symptoms relief and healing. This study explores the comaparative aspect of Mukhapaka and its modern medical counterpart.

KEYWORDS: Mukhapaka, Mukharoga, RAS, Stomatitis, Dosha, Ayurveda

INTRODUCTION-

सर्वस्मिन् मुखे ये भवन्ति ते सर्वसराः। सु.नि.१६/६४^[1]

Oral cavity is gateway of G.I.T. Its mirror of G.I.T. condition. It assist larynx to produce speech. Mukhapaka (Stomatitis) is most common disease of oral cavity. It occurs anywhere in the mouth including the inside of the cheeks, lips, palate, gums, tongue.^[1] In this condition Mukha affected by paka process which is always associated with pitta dosha. In Mukhapaka Pitta dosha, Raktavah and Mamsa are the main dushya.^[2]

Mukha Rogas is pittaja nanatmaja and rakta pradoshaja vikara and around 10% of population is suffering with this problem.^[3] Mukhapaka occurs due to Nutritional deficiency e.g. Vit.B12 deficiency, Folate deficiency, Stress, Illness, Poor oral hygiene, Eating hot food itmes, Leukaemia, Inflammatory bowel disease, Disturbances in G.I. tract like constipation, Poor hygiene etc.^{[4][5]}

In modern life style, excessive intake of spicy foods, acidic food, cold drinks, fast foods etc. and addictions of chewing Betel nut, Gutkha, Tobacco, Smoking etc. have increased incidence of disease pertaining to oral cavity.^{[4][5][6]} Which are characterized as apathyakar ahara in Ayurved disturbs the normal physiology of the body and cause many oral diseases and Mukhapaka is one of them.^[5] The symptoms range from presence of Mouth Ulcers, Pain, Redness and Erosion of Buccal Mucosa, Burning Sensation of Oral Mucosa, Difficulty in chewing Pungent and Hot things.^[7]

To break the samprapti of Mukhapaka, pitta doshahara, rakta prasadaka, vrana shodhaka, vrana ropaka, shothahar chikitsa essensial. As per Ayurveda the line of treatment for Mukhapaka should be pitta shamaka,

shothahar, vedanasthapana, vrana shodhana, vrana ropana, rakta prasadaka, mamsa dhatu pustikar. Stomatitis has become very common problem in the present era. It is very important to have effective, economic and without any side effect medicine on it.^[7]

In modern medicine several mouth paints and gargles, B complex group of drugs and various other treatment like injection submucosal which have their own limitations are being recommended in this disease.^[8] However, Ayurvedic medicine is economical, cost effective and very much helpful to break pathogenesis with relief of sign and symptoms, gradually preventing complications.^[9]

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

AIM-

Aim of this study is to explore and analyze the traditional Ayurvedic management concept of Mukhapaka and compare it with its modern counterpart.

A) PRIMARY OBJECTIVE-

To study the effect of Ayurvedic management in signs and symptoms of Mukhapaka .

B) SECONDARY OBJECTIVE-

To study the etiopathology of Mukhapaka and Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis as per Ayurveda and Modern point of view.

DISEASES REVIEW

SAMANYA HETU

In Samhita or a text there is not described the direct factor causing Mukhapaka separately. There is a common list of causes of 65 Mukharoga among which mukhapaka is the one. Therefore, those causes can be considered as the list of causes of mukhapaka also. The disease which is occupying in all the seven parts of Mukha (Oral cavity), that disease is term as Mukhapaka. . It occurs in all over oral cavity i.e. Mukha. Acharya Charaka has described it as Mukhapaka while Acharya Sushruta and Acharya Vagbhata have described it as Sarvasara.

मात्स्यमहिषवाराहपिशितामकमुलकम् ।

माषसूपदधिकीरसुक्तेक्षुरसफणितम् ॥

अवाक शय्यान च भजतो द्विषतो दन्तधावनम् ।

धूमच्छर्दनगण्डूषानुचितन च सिराव्यधम् ॥ - वा.उ.२१-१,२

SANKHYA SAMPRAPTI

सर्वसरास्तुः वातपित्तकफशोणितनिमित्ताः । सु. नि. १६-६४

According to Acharya Sushruta there are 3 types of sarvasara mukharogas i.e. mukhapaka. Sharangadhara mentioned 5 types. And according to Vagbhata there are 8 types of Mukhapaka.

Sarvasara Mukha rogas are named as “Mukha- Paka”. Occur by spreading completely in the Mukha so only named as Sarvasara much rogas.

TYPES OF MUKHAPAKA-

VATAJA MUKHAPAKA

स्फोटैः सतोदैर्वदनं समन्ताद्यस्या चित्तं सर्वसरः स वातात् । सु.नि.16-64

The vitiated vata dosha causes a single or multiple ulcers in the Oral mucosa with acute inflammatory changes. The disease is progressive in nature, very painful, mucosa becomes dry and rough. The associated symptoms are inflamed lips tongue and palate, difficulty in opening the mouth and sensitivity to cold items.

PITTAJA MUKHAPAKA

रक्तैः सदाहैस्तनुभिः सपीतैर्यस्याचितन चापि स पित्तकोपात॥ सु.नि.१६-६५

The vitiated pitta dosha causes inflammation and ulceration of oral mucosa. Smaller reddish yellow papules develop throughout the mouth. causes severe burn- ing pain. altered taste (Bitter mouth), difficulty in mastication and deglutition.^[11]

KAPHAJ MUKHAPAKA

कण्डुयुतैरल्परुजैः सवर्णैर्यस्याचितं चापि स वै कफैः। सु.नि.16-65

The vitiated Kapha dosha produces inflammation and ulceration in the oral mucosa, The mouth become sweet sticky with itching sensation and negligible pain. Small cysts or tumours develop and become more severe by compression and excision.

SANNIPATAJA MUKHAPAKA

मुखपाको भवेत्सास्त्रोः सर्वैः सर्वकृतिमलैः । वा.उ.21/62

All the symptoms of Tridosha and Rakta Dosha are present in this disease.

RAKTAJA MUKHAPAKA

रक्तेन पित्तोदित एक एव कैश्चित् प्रदिष्टो मुखपाक संज्ञः । सु.नि. 16-66

Signs and symptoms is like pittaja mukhapaka.

SAMANYA CHIKITSA

मुखपाके शिरावेधः शिरसश्च विरेचनम।यो.र.भा.२पा.५१३

मुखपाके सिराकर्म शिरःकायविरेचनम।

मुत्रतैल घृतक्षौद्र क्षीरैश्च कवलग्रहः॥च.चि.२६-२०४

In every type of Mukhapaka, after the shodhana karma like siravedha, shirovirechana, kayavirechana etc. Mukhadhavana, Charvana, Pratisarna, Kashayapana, Kavalgraha and Abhyantara Chikitsa should be use.

SAMPRAPTI:

PATHYA

तृणधान्यं यवा मुद्गाः कुलथा जांगलो रसः । बहुपत्री कारवेल्लं पटोल बालमुलकम् ॥ कर्पूरनीरं तांबुलं तप्ताम्बू खदिरोघृतम् । कतुतिक्तो च वर्गोयं मित्रास्यात्मुखरोगिणाम् ॥ यो.र.

AHARA		VIAHARA	RASA
Bitter gourd	Old rice	Tambulsevana	Katu
Surpantgaurd	Wheat		Tikta
Nil camphor	Bean		
Khadir	Horse		
ghrit	Gram		

APATHYA

दंतकाष्ठं स्नानमम्लं मत्स्यमानूपमामिषम् । दधि क्षीरं गुडं माषं रुक्षान्नं कंठनाशनम् ॥ अधोमुखेन शयनं गुर्वभिष्यंदकारि च । मुखरोगेषु सर्वेषु दिवानिद्रां च वर्जयेत् ॥ यो.र.

AHARA		VIAHARA	RASA
Curd	Non oily things	Cold water bath	Katu
Milk & derivatives	Abhishyandi	Tooth brushing	
Gud	Fish	Hard chewing	
Sweets	Flesh of water livings	Sleeping in prone position	
Black gram		Day time sleep	

SAMANYA CHIKITSA^[13]

मुखपाके शिरावेधः शिरसश्च विरेचनम्।यो.र.भा.२पा.५१३

मुखपाके सिराकर्म शिरःकायविरेचनम्।

मुत्रतैल घृतक्षौद्र क्षीरिञ्च कवलग्रहः ॥च.चि.२६-२०४

In every type of Mukhapaka, after the shodhana karma like siravedha, shirovirechana, kayavirechana etc. Mukhadhavana, Charvana, Pratisarna, Kashayapana, Kavalgraha and Abhyantara Chikitsa should be use.^[12]

Herbal Remedies

Haritaki (Terminalia chebula) – Antibacterial and healing properties

Yashtimadhu(Glycyrrhiza glabra)- anti inflammatory and soothing properties

Triphala- act as a antimicrobial and detoxifier

Aloe vera gel- cooling and healing effect

Ghee and honey application- pain relief and promotes healing

Ayurvedic Treatment

Kavala-Gandusha –

Kavala Gandusha is an Ayurvedic practice that involves holding a medicinal liquid, typically oil or herbal concoctions, in the mouth for a short period of time to promote oral health and overall well-being. It is a traditional technique rooted in Ayurveda, used for oral detoxification, cleaning the mouth, and balancing the doshas (Vata, Pitta, and Kapha).

Benefits of Kavala Gandusha

- Improves Oral Health
- Detoxification
- strengthens Gums and Teeth
- Balances Doshas
- Improves Digestion

Ayurvedic drugs^[15]

Herbal Decoctions: herbs such as neem, babul, or turmeric are boiled with water to create an herbal decoction, which is used in Gandusha.

Herbal Oils: Medicinal oils may be prepared by infusing oils such as sesame or coconut with herbs like neem, clove, and turmeric, creating a potent oil for Gandusha.

Powdered Herbs: In some cases, powders of herbs like Triphala or Amla may be mixed with water or oil and used in the Gandusha process.

Pratisarana

Pratisaran can be interpreted as the act of rubbing or massaging the gums, teeth, and other parts of the mouth with specific herbal pastes, oils, or powders.

Herbal powders- These can be made from babul, neem, turmeric, clove, cinnamon, or mint, which have antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties.

Oil-based applications- Sesame oil or coconut oil are often used for rubbing the gums and teeth. These oils are believed to help in detoxifying the mouth and promoting oral health.

Pastes- A paste of turmeric and clove or other specific herbs can be applied to the teeth and gums as part of Pratisaran for its antibacterial and healing properties.

Benefits

- Improves Oral Health
- Detoxification
- strengthens Gums and Teeth
- Balances Doshas
- Improves Digestion

RECURRENT APHTHOUS STOMATITIS^{[16][117]}

RAS anywhere in the oral cavity is painful and is one of the most common oral ailment. The disease is characterized by recurring painful ulcers of the mouth that are round or ovoid and are surrounded by inflammatory halos with the symptoms of Burning sensation, Ulceration, Redness and Erosion of buccal mucosa, Difficulty in chewing, Pain at affected site.^{[8][18][19]}

An inflammatory condition of the mucous membrane of the oral mucosa with or without ulceration is referred to as a Stomatitis.

Recurrent Aphthous Minor, which is the most common form of the disease and this one is referred as the Canker sore by public.

The Aphthous Ulcer begins as a single or multiple superficial erosions have a well circumscribed margin surrounded by erythematous halo.

The lesion is typically very painful so that is commonly interferes with eating for several days. That vary in size from 2.3mm to over 10mm in diameter. The most common sites of occurrence are the Buccal and Lingual sulci, Tongue, Soft palate, Pharynx and Gingival, all locations of labial mucosa.^{[8][19]}

The ulcers themselves generally persist for 14 to 21 days and then heal gradually with little or no evidence of scarring.

Types of Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis^{[18]:}

1. Minor Aphthous Stomatitis:

- Most common form (about 80% of cases).
- Typically small ulcers (less than 1 cm) that heal within 7–10 days without scarring.

2. Major Aphthous Stomatitis:

- Larger ulcers (greater than 1 cm).
- May cause significant pain and take longer to heal (2–6 weeks).
- Often leave scarring after healing.

3. Herpetiform Aphthous Stomatitis:

- Numerous small ulcers (clustered together).
- The ulcers are smaller but can appear in groups, sometimes merging into larger ones.
- Tends to affect individuals more frequently, with multiple outbreaks over time.

MANAGEMENT OF RAS^[19]

In Modern medicine several mouth paints and gargles, B complex group of drugs and various other treatment like injection submucosal which have their own limitations are being recommended in this disease.^{[9][13]}

Children and adult sometimes may miss dose and medication may have some complications. Also, this treatment does not prevent from recurrence of disease, and its has side effects like constipation, stomach upset, diarrhea, excessive urination, vomiting, nausea which can occur due to consumption of Vitamin B12.^{[14][19]}

VITAMIN B12

Vitamin B is effective in treating mouth ulcer in addition to its effectiveness, it also significantly reduces the possibility of recurrence, it accelerate ulcer healing and shortance the cause of treatment.^{[9][10][12]}

Side Effects- ^{[14][19][25][26]}

- Constipation
- Stomach Upset
- Nausea
- Vomiting
- Excessive Urination

DISCUSSION

Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis (RAS) is a multifactorial condition that involves complex interactions between genetic, immune, and environmental factors. The condition can cause significant discomfort and affect one's quality of life. While both conventional and Ayurvedic treatments offer various benefits for symptom relief, a holistic approach that includes dietary adjustments, stress management, and appropriate medical intervention may provide the best outcomes for managing RAS in the long term.

CONCLUSION

The study of Mukhapaka offers valuable insights into traditional methods for maintaining oral health, many of which have been validated by modern science for their effectiveness in preventing and treating oral diseases. Ayurveda's focus on balance, prevention, and the use of natural remedies provides a holistic framework for oral hygiene that aligns with modern dentistry's focus on prevention and care.

Ultimately, the study of Mukhapaka and its modern counterpart highlights the potential for integrating traditional and modern dental practices to enhance oral health. By combining the scientific advancements of modern dentistry with the natural, preventative techniques of Ayurveda, we can offer a more comprehensive and personalized approach to oral care, improving both the health of the mouth and the overall well-being of individuals.

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